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Cover: graphic reworking of a sheet from Van Dyck's Italian Sketchbook depicting Sofonisba Anguissola

THEORY AND CRITICISM OF LITERATURE AND ARTS

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A Study in Sketches:
Gunta Stölzl's Early Years in Munich (1914-1919)

MIRJAM DECKERS
University of Groningen

An artist in the making

In 2019, the 100th anniversary of the Bauhaus, the legendary German design school founded in 1919 by architect Walter Gropius, was celebrated worldwide. For one thing, the discourse has been concerned with the position of female artists at the school.¹ Gunta Stölzl (1897-1983) was one of the most important ones of them, as she was appointed *Jungmeister* of the weaving workshop in Dessau in 1927, an exceptionally high position for a woman at that time. An intriguing story that certainly deserves attention. However, in the past three years that I have been working with the archives of Gunta Stölzl, I have come to question why so little attention has been paid to Stölzl's artistic development as a whole.² As I will demonstrate here, almost exclusively all of the research that has been conducted is occupied with Stölzl's years at the Bauhaus (1919-1931). This is understandable, as the Bauhaus is an established and recognizable name, and a fixed position within the history of art and design. Furthermore, Stölzl's intriguing position as a female *Meister* has received increased attention within the current and pressing discussion on reinstalling female artists

¹ See for example U. Müller, *Bauhaus-Frauen. Meisterinnen in Kunst, Handwerk und Design*, second revised edition, Elisabeth Sandmann Verlag, Munich, 2019 (first published 2009); E. Otto, *Haunted Bauhaus. Occult Spirituality, Gender Fluidity, Queer Identities and Radical Politics*, The MIT Press, Cambridge (Mass.)/London, 2019, and in particular the third chapter 'Bauhaus Femininities in Transformation'; E. Otto and P. Rössler (eds.), *Bauhaus Bodies*, Bloomsbury Visual Arts, New York, 2019; E. Otto and P. Rössler, *Bauhaus Women. A Global Perspective*, Bloomsbury Publishing, London, 2019; P. Rössler, *Bauhausmädels*, Taschen, Cologne, 2019; the biography by I. Radewaldt, *Gunta Stölzl. Pionierin der Bauhausweberei*, Weimarer Verlagsgesellschaft, Weimar, 2019. A selection of exhibitions: the large retrospective of Anni Albers at Tate Modern in London (11 October 2018 – 27 January 2019), the small exhibition on Gunta Stölzl at Wall House #2 in Groningen, the Netherlands (30 March – 1 September 2019), and the exhibition on Bauhaus weavers Kitty van der Mijll Dekker, Gunta Stölzl, Lisbeth Östreicher and Otti Berger at Textielmuseum Tilburg, the Netherlands (25 May – 3 November 2019).

² The largest part of Gunta Stölzl's archive is in possession of her family, who provided me with unlimited access during my research. In particular, I thank Stölzl's daughters Yael Aloni and Monika Stadler for the enormous work they have been putting into the preservation of their mother's legacy, and for their invaluable help.

within the art historical canon. However, Stölzl's years at the Bauhaus make up only a relatively small part of her whole artistic career: this spanned from roughly 1914, when she enrolled the Kunstgewerbeschule in Munich, until her death in Zurich in 1983, at the age of 86, after she had had a career as a professional handweaver in Switzerland for over 30 years. Stölzl has thus not yet been regarded as an artist in her own right, outside of the discourse on the Bauhaus.

This article is a first step in that direction, proposing to expand the research that has been done thus far with regard to Stölzl. In order to do so, we will go back to the very start of Stölzl's career, that is, her early years in Munich, when she studied at the local Kunstgewerbeschule, and created numerous works on paper, including drawings and paintings. No less than around 250 of these works still survive in her estate, but none of them have been studied until now. They are largely unknown, do not belong to public art collections, and are rarely exhibited. In the context of this article, I can show only a small selection of these virtually unknown works on paper, but I am hoping to provide a new point of entry for paying more attention to the full career of this artist, adding a new time frame (1914-1919) and a new medium (work on paper) to the discourse on Stölzl.³ Adding to that, this article also introduces Stölzl's own writings from the years 1914 to 1919 – diaries, lecture notes and letters – that illustrate her early artistic interests and aspirations. These writings have not yet been published in the context of a research project examining Stölzl's artistic career outside of the Bauhaus. The writings and works on paper from Stölzl's archives together contribute to a more complete image of Stölzl's artistic trajectory and help in updating her biography. Furthermore, they may also shine a new light on Stölzl's Bauhaus years, informing us about the artistic baggage the student brought with her when she entered the school in 1919.

Status quo of Stölzl research: Stölzl as Bauhaus weaver

Before turning to the archive, I will briefly discuss the current status quo of research on Gunta Stölzl. What is the picture of her artistic career that we are we adding to in this

³ Stölzl herself did not always give a title to these works on paper. In cases where she did not explicitly sign her work, I have used the titles as they currently appear in Stölzl's online work catalogue. In January 2021, I launched a first version of this online catalogue, which contains all of Stölzl's known works, spanning the years 1914-1983. The catalogue was made in close collaboration with Stölzl's family members and is available via the Swiss platform Kleio. At the moment of writing, access to this catalogue can be requested via www.guntastolzl.org/About/Catalogue/ or via archiveguntastolzl@gmail.com.

article? Adelgunde ('Gunta') Stölzl was born in 1897 in Munich.⁴ She entered the local Kunstgewerbeschule in 1914, where she studied glass painting, decorative painting, ceramics, and art history.⁵ In the early months of 1917, in the midst of the First World War, Stölzl decided to volunteer as a Red Cross nurse. From the summer of 1917 onwards, she traveled throughout Germany and Europe, witnessing the horrors of the Great War first-hand. After the end of the war, Stölzl returned to Munich, disillusioned by the massive devastation, and longing for something new and constructive. She picked up her studies again in January 1919. She participated in the Munich reform movement that was led by the Kunstgewerbeschule director Richard Riemerschmid. However, after reading the Bauhaus manifesto, written by Gropius in April 1919, she left the Kunstgewerbeschule for good, one year before her graduation, to enter the newly opened school in Weimar in September as one of its first students.⁶ The Bauhaus proposed a new unity between '*Kunst*' (art) and '*Handwerk*' (craft), and the manifesto proclaimed that all artists should return to craftsmanship and to workshops ('*Werkstätten*').⁷ After the mandatory preliminary course, Stölzl enrolled the textile workshop, which she helped to establish, in 1920. This workshop became the 'women's class', for Gropius tried to reduce the amount of women to be admitted to the workshops, despite the Bauhaus explicitly being open for both men and women. In the textile workshop, the Bauhaus weaving students wanted to turn weaving into an acknowledged form modern craft, equal to all of the other (male-dominated) Bauhaus workshops. They thus increasingly focused on functional fabrics for the interior,

⁴ Her father was a progressive school principle, and a friend and supporter of Georg Kerschensteiner, a Munich-based educational theorist who advocated a pragmatic approach to education, including more hands-on learning and manual labor. See also I. Radewaldt, *Gunta Stölzl*, p. 12.

⁵ Sometimes, it is stated that Stölzl entered the school in 1913. Stölzl's family cannot confirm the exact year. I follow the most recent biography by Ingrid Radewaldt (2019) here.

⁶ For a full discussion of Stölzl's life, I refer to I. Radewaldt, *Gunta Stölzl* (2019).

⁷ W. Gropius, *Programm des staatlichen Bauhauses in Weimar*, inhouse-publication, Weimar, 1919. It is important to realize that this idea of returning to craft and to the workshops was not entirely new, but rather part of a discussion concerning the position of the craftsperson that had been going on since the Industrial Revolution and which also seeped into arts education. For a discussion of the situation in Munich, see J. Maciuika, *Before the Bauhaus: Architecture, Politics, and the German State, 1890-1920*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2005. For an analysis of how this discussion influenced German art schools in the early twentieth century, including the Bauhaus, see H.M. Wingler (ed.), *Kunstschulreform 1900-1933: Bauhaus Weimar Dessau Berlin Kunstschule Debschitz, München, Frankfurter Kunstschule, Akademie für Kunst und Kunstgewerbe Breslau, Reimann-Schule Berlin*, Gebrüder Mann Verlag, Berlin, 1977.

deploying revolutionary materials such as cellophane, and created textiles that were meant to integrate within the interior as a whole, true to the Bauhaus philosophy.⁸ After the Bauhaus had to move to Dessau due to the changing political climate in Weimar during the course of 1925, Stölzl was first made *Werkmeister*, and eventually *Jungmeister* in 1927, the highest position a woman until then had held at the Bauhaus.⁹ She would keep this position until she resigned from the school in October 1931, after an accumulation of both personal and political controversies.¹⁰ She left Germany for good and moved to Zurich, where she established her own handweaving workshop, which she managed until her retirement in 1967 at the age of 70. Until her death in 1983, she remained an avid weaver of wall hangings and tapestries, while also creating numerous drawings and sketches.

Stölzl's life and work were discovered remarkably late, as is the fate of most Bauhaus women. Whereas the Bauhaus itself was rediscovered from the mid-1950s onward, causing Stölzl to partake in exhibitions on the school and to sell her work to numerous museums worldwide, scholars have ignored her during her lifetime.¹¹ After Stölzl's death, it was her family, in particular her two daughters Yael Aloni and Monika Stadler, that put effort into monographic exhibitions and literature, resulting in the traveling exhibition *Gunta Stölzl: Weberei am Bauhaus und aus eigener Werkstatt* and a catalogue by the Bauhaus-Archiv Berlin in 1987.¹² Ten years later, in 1997, the seminal retrospective *Gunta Stölzl. Meisterin*

⁸ For a concise history of the Bauhaus weaving workshop, see M. Droste, 'Anpassung und Eigensinn. Die Webereiwerkstatt des Bauhauses', exh. cat. *Das Bauhaus webt. Die Textilwerkstatt am Bauhaus*, G+H Verlag, Berlin, 1998, pp. 11-20.

⁹ In Weimar, there had been a somewhat hierarchical distinction between a *Werkmeister*, responsible for the practical and technical management of the workshop, and a *Formmeister*, who had the overall artistic responsibility. Shortly after the Bauhaus opened in Dessau, the structure of *Werkmeister* and *Formmeister* was replaced. Former Bauhaus graduates from Weimar took over the leadership of the workshops as *Jungmeister*, while the position of *Werkmeister* was replaced by apprenticeships. See M. Siebenbrodt and L. Schöbe, *Bauhaus: 1919-1933, Weimar-Dessau-Berlin*, Parkstone Press, New York, 2009, pp. 40-41.

¹⁰ For a recent and elaborate account of these controversies, see I. Radewaldt, *Gunta Stölzl*, pp. 144-156.

¹¹ The most notable early exhibitions are *Arbeiten aus der Weberei des Bauhauses* at the Bauhaus-Archiv, Darmstadt (12 May – 14 June 1964), *50 Jahre Bauhaus* at the Württembergischer Kunstverein, Stuttgart (5 May – 28 July 1968), and the small solo exhibition *Gunta Stadler-Stölzl: Wandteppiche und Entwürfe 1921-1976* at the Bauhaus-Archiv, Berlin (20 November 1976 – 30 January 1977). Early museums to acquire Stölzl's work were the Busch-Reisinger Museum in Cambridge, Massachusetts, that bought a wall hanging (1923) in 1949, followed by the Museum of Modern Art in New York, that purchased a wall hanging (1924) in 1958.

¹² Bauhaus Archiv Berlin, exh. cat. *Gunta Stölzl: Weberei am Bauhaus und aus eigener Werkstatt*, Kupfergraben Verlag, Berlin, 1987.

am Bauhaus Dessau was organized by Stiftung Bauhaus Dessau, accompanied by the most extensive publication on Stölzl's oeuvre until today. The catalogue contains a comprehensive biography, describing Stölzl's life in great detail.¹³ Although a large part of the biography is devoted to her Bauhaus years, it is still one of the few biographies that actually discusses Stölzl's full career as a weaver.¹⁴ Nevertheless, the focus of both of these two monographic exhibitions was on Stölzl's Bauhaus textiles.

Apart from publications prompted or written by family members, Stölzl started to emerge in art historical literature from the 1990s onwards, but only slowly. What stands out is that these publications appear *exclusively* within the context of the Bauhaus and more specifically in the context of Bauhaus women. With the rise of feminist art history in the 1990s, the Bauhaus weaving workshop was rediscovered as the place where female Bauhaus artists renewed modern textile design.¹⁵ It has also been researched as the place of gender inequalities: women were forced into their own workshop to practice the 'feminine' craft of weaving.¹⁶ Within these discussions, Gunta Stölzl often acts as a *pars pro toto* not only for the weaving workshop, but also for the unequal position of women at the Bauhaus. Through her leading role and her rather exceptional position as *Jungmeister*, Gunta Stölzl is regarded as a metonymy – standing in for the workshop and the interests and practices of the weaver – and at the same time as an exception – being the workshop's first female master.¹⁷

¹³ I. Radewaldt and M. Stadler, 'Gunta Stölzl. Biographie', exh. cat. *Gunta Stölzl. Meisterin am Bauhaus Dessau*, Verlag Gerd Hatje, Ostfildern, 1997, pp. 10-86.

¹⁴ This is perhaps not a surprise when one takes into account that it was written mainly by art historian Ingrid Radewaldt, who knew Stölzl personally.

¹⁵ Cfr. S. Wortmann Weltge, *Bauhaus Textiles. Women Artists and the Weaving Workshop*, Thames & Hudson, London, 1993; M. Droste and M. Ludewig (eds.), exh. cat. *Das Bauhaus webt. Die Textilwerkstatt am Bauhaus*, G+H Verlag, Berlin, 1998; U. Müller, *Bauhaus-Frauen. Meisterinnen in Kunst, Handwerk und Design*, Elisabeth Sandmann Verlag, Munich, 2009, with a second, revised edition in 2019; T. Smith, *Bauhaus Weaving Theory. From Feminine Craft to Mode of Design*, University of Minnesota Press, Minneapolis, 2014.

¹⁶ Cfr. A. Baumhoff, 'Die Alibi-Meisterin', *Bauhaus*, edited by Jeannine Fiedler and Peter Feierabend, Könemann, Cologne, 2000, pp. 354-357; A. Baumhoff, *The Gendered World of the Bauhaus. The Politics of Power at the Weimar Republic's Premier Art Institute, 1919-1932*, Peter Lang, Frankfurt am Main, 2001.

¹⁷ The term 'metonymy' is also used by T'ai Smith, see T. Smith, 'A Collective and its Individuals: The Bauhaus and its Women', exh. cat. *Modern Women: Women Artists at the Museum of Modern Art*, Museum of Modern Art, New York, 2010, pp. 158-173.

There are only very few sources that move beyond this Bauhaus-oriented perspective on Stölzl, discussing some of the work that she did before or after the period 1919-1931. Besides the extensive biography in the catalogue from 1997, daughters Stadler and Aloni published *Gunta Stölzl. Bauhausmeisterin* (2009), followed by an English edition issued by the Museum of Modern Art in New York. The book takes a biographical perspective, focusing on the period 1917 to 1931, that is, mostly on the Bauhaus. Despite its narrow scope, it is an important publication as Aloni and Stadler included letters and diary entries from Stölzl's archive that had not been published before. Nevertheless, similar to the catalogue in 1997, the book was published within the context of the Bauhaus – 2009 marking its 90th anniversary – and still concentrated on Stölzl's Bauhaus years. In 2019, Ingrid Radewaldt published a full biography, *Gunta Stölzl. Pionierin der Bauhausweberei*, on the occasion of the 100th anniversary of the Bauhaus. As the title already suggests, despite covering Stölzl's entire life, the largest part of the biography was devoted to Stölzl at the Bauhaus.

To summarize, the Bauhaus women, including Gunta Stölzl, have received increasing and much-needed attention, reaching a peak in 2019. Undoubtedly, Stölzl was indeed one of the most important female Bauhaus artists, and her story of rising from a student to the position of *Meister* is certainly worth telling. However, now that she and other Bauhaus women are rediscovered, it is time to move beyond this rather limited perspective on her life and work. I will now turn to Stölzl's archive in order to do just that. For rather than Stölzl appearing at the Bauhaus out of the blue and moving into obscurity after leaving the school, her archive tells us a different and much more colorful story. By looking at what she did and what she created before she knocked on the door of the Bauhaus, we might make a start with giving her the full attention as an artist on her own that she deserves. A case that probably could be made for other Bauhaus women as well.

An artist-in-bud in a flourishing art center

Before discussing Stölzl's artistic work on paper from the years 1914 to 1919, I turn to some of her writings from this same period, to illustrate Stölzl's familiarity with the Munich art scene.¹⁸ The picture that appears from these writings is that of a cultural omnivore in her early adult years, devouring the many artistic flavors in her hometown, visiting

¹⁸ Some of Stölzl's writings are also in the possession of the (currently closed) Bauhaus-Archiv Berlin, but the family archive holds copies, of which I gratefully made use now that the Bauhaus-Archiv is inaccessible.

influential venues such as Galerie Caspari for modern art, and the Neue Pinakothek, which housed artworks created after 1800 exclusively, including many Impressionist paintings.¹⁹ She would also read up on a broad range of modern artistic expressions and artists. Munich proved fruitful ground for artists in the early twentieth century. The city housed numerous influential galleries and museums, but was also home to the members of Der Blaue Reiter, founded in 1911 by Wassily Kandinsky, who would become a teacher at the Bauhaus in 1922, and Franz Marc. Moreover, in 1907 the Deutscher Werkbund, often mentioned as an important predecessor to the Bauhaus, was founded in the city by, among others, Richard Riemerschmid.²⁰ Stölzl's writings demonstrates that she was familiar with these developments in Munich and was inspired by them.

To her elder brother Erwin Stölzl, who served as a soldier throughout the war, she wrote in the autumn of 1916:

“Wegen dem Fliegerbesuch sind jetzt beide Pinakotheken geschlossen, das ist scheußlich besonders um die modernen Franzosen tut mir leid, die ich doch noch immer am meisten schätze, um C'zanne [sic], Monnet [sic], Manet, Van Gogh und Hodler,”²¹

As can be read here, Stölzl held a particular interest in French (Post-)Impressionism and Expressionism, and especially Vincent van Gogh during these years. An advice that she gave already earlier in a letter to her friend Ingeborg further illustrates this:

“Wenn du einmal ein bisschen Zeit hast und da ich vermute, daß du dich noch ebenso für Kunst interessierst so schau, daß du etwas von den Bahnbrechern der Modernen Kunst von den französischen Impressionisten Manet Monnet Degard

¹⁹ On the somewhat surprising success of French Impressionism in Germany, see P. Hook, *The Ultimate Trophy. How The Impressionist Painting Conquered the World*, Prestel, Munich/London, 2009, pp. 92-119.

²⁰ S. West, *The Visual Arts in Germany 1890-1937: Utopia and Despair*, Manchester University Press, Manchester, 2000, pp. 143-144.

²¹ Gunta Stölzl in a letter to her brother Erwin Stölzl, dated autumn 1916, emphasis by Gunta Stölzl. As one will see, Stölzl's attitude to punctuation was rather casual, especially in diaries and letters to friends and family. I have not altered the original.

[sic] Delacroix Daumier Millet Gaugain [sic], van Gogh Cézanne zu sehen bekommst.”²²

In the same letter, she mentions that she followed lectures in modern art by professor Josef Popp, who also discussed artists such as Manet, Monet, Picasso, and Cézanne.²³ There are also diary entries that testify specifically to her knowledge of the German and Munich artworld. For example, her diary from March 1918 reads the following:

“Die Ausstellung bei Caspari [Georg Caspari’s gallery for modern and contemporary art, M.D.] der Neuen Secession hat mich sehr ergriffen, hat mir sehr viel gegeben. Kubin, Dora Polster und andere, alles ganz starke Expressionisten, es waren leider nur kleine Dinge, keine große dekorative Malerei, [Albert] Weisgerber, [Franz] Marc, diese Leute fehlen eben doch ganz, so wirklich hervorragend starke Persönlichkeiten. Das Werk von Fr[it]z. Burger hat mich auch stark interessiert, obwohl ich viel nicht verstehe und wohl nie verstehen werde.”²⁴

Here, we learn that Stölzl not only visited local galleries that showed contemporary artists, but also read up on the latest art historical publications in Germany, such as the work of Munich-based art historian Fritz Burger, who published, among other things, on Cézanne and Hodler²⁵, two painters whose work Stölzl loved to see in the Neue Pinakothek, as she wrote in the letter to her brother quoted earlier.

²² Gunta Stölzl in a letter to her friend Ingeborg (surname unknown), dated Munich, 26 December 1915.

²³ Ibid., these lectures were given at the Polytechnische Schule in Munich, next to the Kunstgewerbeschule. On her testimony from 1919, signed by director Riemerschmid, Popp’s course in art history is mentioned again. This testimony is in the Gunta Stölzl Archive.

²⁴ Gunta Stölzl in her diary, dated 28 March 1918. At the time of this writing, both Albert Weisgerber and Franz Marc had been killed in the War. Who also participated in this exhibition with no less than 30 works, but to whom Stölzl does not refer, is Paul Klee, who lived in Munich at the time, and had been involved with *Der Blaue Reiter*. Klee would also become Stölzl’s teacher and later colleague at the Bauhaus in Weimar and in Dessau. See also the exhibition catalogue: *Galerie Caspari, Muenchener Neue Secession. Grapische Ausstellung*, exh. cat, C. Wolf & Sohn, Munich, 1918.

²⁵ F. Burger, *Cézanne und Hodler. Einführung in die Probleme der Malerei der Gegenwart*, 2 volumes, Delphin-Verlag, Munich, 1913. Another work that Stölzl could have read was Burger’s highly popular *Einführung in die moderne Kunst* (1917), published posthumously after Burger was killed during the Battle of Verdun.

One of the names that recurs in Stölzl's writings is Vincent van Gogh. Many of the Munich-based modern artists, not in the least the members of Der Blaue Reiter, were inspired by Van Gogh, whose fame rose remarkably fast in the early years of the twentieth century, and in Germany in particular.²⁶ The early translation of Van Gogh's letters to his brother Theo into German contributed to this: a first anthology compiled by Margarete Mauthner was published in 1906, followed by a two-volume edition by Paul Cassirer in 1914. These letters were widely read in Germany and promoted the image of the artist as the misunderstood and poor genius. This image was voiced by the German art historian Julius Meier-Graefe in his popular biography of the Dutch painter published by Reinhard Piper in Munich in 1910, which was reprinted multiple times. In one of her notebooks, dated 23 April 1916, Stölzl devoted a longer entry to this artist, titled 'Briefe v. van Gogh'. She had obtained an edition of his letters as a Christmas present in 1915, and described in her letter to her friend Ingeborg: "...die Briefe van Gogh's. Ich weiß nicht ob Du diesen großen Maler den Überwinder d. Impressionismus und Vater des Expressionismus kennst, ich schätze ihn ungeheuer, er ist ein Fanatiker ein Schaffender ein nietzschischer Geist."²⁷ She explains in her notebook why Van Gogh is her artistic ideal, how his life exemplifies the "unbridgeable gap between art and life" and how the true artist "can never be at the center of life", how she admires his hard and passionate work despite all of his discomforts and ailments.²⁸ Other writings testify to her admiration for his work, especially his use of color and his preference for contemporary working people – depicting them *while* they are

²⁶ The Städel Museum in Frankfurt am Main organized the exhibition *Making Van Gogh. Geschichte einer deutschen Liebe* (23 October 2019 – 16 February 2020) which addressed this intriguing early reception of Van Gogh in Germany. For the catalogue, see A. Eiling and F. Krämer, *Making Van Gogh. Geschichte einer deutschen Liebe*, exh. cat., Hirmer Verlag, Munich, 2019. After the tragic death of both Vincent and Theo van Gogh, Theo's wife, Johanna van Gogh-Bonger, devoted herself to the promotion of her late brother-in-law, including single-handedly documenting and selling his work, as well as editing and publishing the correspondence between the two brothers. She was a crucial actor in the rise of Van Gogh's popularity. Recently, a Dutch biography was published: H. Luijten, *Alles voor Vincent*, Prometheus, Amsterdam, 2019. For the specific role that the Thannhauser Gallery, which opened in Munich in 1909, played in the early reception of Van Gogh, see S. Koldehoff and C. Stolwijk, *The Thannhauser Gallery. Marketing Van Gogh*, Mercatorfonds, Brussels/Van Gogh Museum, Amsterdam, 2017. For the role of Paul Cassirer in Berlin, see W. Feilchenfeldt, *Vincent van Gogh & Paul Cassirer, Berlin: The Reception of Van Gogh in Germany from 1901 to 1914*, Waanders, Zwolle, 1988.

²⁷ Gunta Stölzl in a letter to her friend Ingeborg (surname unknown), dated Munich, 26 December 1915.

²⁸ Notebook no. 8 (October 1915-June 1916) in the Gunta Stölzl Archive, pp. 73-77.

working, rather than letting them pose for him.²⁹ As she writes in 1916: “Arbeiter, Menschen unsrer Zeit, die Tätigkeit um ihres Ausdrucks willen. Den Menschen in seinen einfachsten Bewegungen in seiner Umgebung, aber das Herausbringen, so daß es den Menschen einfach aufaßt – ergreift.”³⁰ A similar interest in everyday people being at work, as we will see, evidently recurs in Stölzl’s early drawings.

As far as I am aware, Stölzl wrote nothing specifically on her decision to enter the Bauhaus in 1919. However, she did describe her increasing doubts towards her studies at the Kunstgewerbeschule. Already in January 1917, before leaving for the Red Cross, she wrote to her brother that certain aspects of her education were “too *kunstgewerblich*” for her, and that she instead hoped to go to the more modern Reimann Schule in Berlin after the summer: “Er sind dort sehr feine Professoren und es soll vielmehr Zug drinnen sein – viel moderner gut modern, impressionistisch – expressionistisch.”³¹ The Reimann Schule in Berlin, founded in 1902, was a private school that strove for a unification of art and applied arts in contemporary design through practice-based teaching, an approach resembling the Deutscher Werkbund as well as the later Bauhaus.³² Hence, already in 1917 Stölzl seriously considered leaving the path of ‘*Kunstgewerbe*’, which was unsatisfactory and not modern enough to her, two years before moving to the Bauhaus. Although we do not know why Stölzl eventually preferred the Bauhaus over Berlin, her letters demonstrate that she had already been aiming for an education that was oriented more towards modern design. Moreover, whereas the diaries and letters quoted earlier testified to her interest in (neo-)impressionist and expressionist art practices, in this letter Stölzl seems to express the wish to also incorporate some of these interests in her own work. At the same time, one must not forget that art academies in Germany became slowly more accessible for women only from 1919 onwards, after the Weimar Constitution. Before that, they were restricted to schools of applied arts, such as the Kunstgewerbeschule in Munich, and generally not

²⁹ In her diary dated 10 June 1919, she describes a Bavarian landscape as a “Farbenpracht”, because it looks like a “Van Gogh’s Kleeacker”.

³⁰ Notebook no. 8 (October 1915-June 1916) in the Gunta Stölzl Archive, p. 75.

³¹ Gunta Stölzl in a letter to her brother Erwin, dated 26 January 1917, emphasis by Gunta Stölzl.

³² In that same year, a similar school, the Debschitz-Schule was founded in Munich, with, among others, Dora Polster as one of its students, whose work Stölzl referred to in the aforementioned description of the exhibition at Caspari’s in 1918. Due to financial circumstances, the Debschitz-Schule was closed already in 1914, which might explain why Stölzl did not attend this school in her hometown. Cfr. H.M. Wingler (ed.), *Kunstschulreform 1900-1933* (1977) for more information on this school, the Reimann Schule, and similar initiatives in Germany.

allowed into the education of ‘autonomous’ art.³³ Moreover, the image of the artist as a genius outside of society – the insurmountable division between art and life that Stölzl herself described in her notebook with regard to Van Gogh, where she also relates ‘life’ to her wish of starting a family– made the domain of art even less accessible for women with artistic aspirations, given what society expected from them.³⁴ Stölzl’s own early vision on these gender roles and what she envisioned for herself, a vision involving complex and personal factors, deserves to be discussed in more detail in the future. For now, it can be concluded that she wanted to learn something that was more in line with the developments in modern art while also being accessible for her as a woman. A school such as the Reimann Schule or the Bauhaus, both of which proclaimed a modern unification of art and craft, closing Van Gogh’s gap between art and life, must have been music to Stölzl’s ears: a place where she could follow her artistic aspirations.

Working class heroes

In what remains, I aim to further demonstrate the modern tendencies Stölzl aspired to by turning to the early works on paper that she created in her spare time, around 250 watercolors and pencil sketches. It is remarkable that Stölzl herself preserved so many of them, especially since she threw away almost all of her assignments for the Kunstgewerbeschule – an indication of how much she distanced herself from it. The works on paper that she kept, on the other hand, must have been of value to her.³⁵ These were

³³ A unification between the Kunstgewerbeschule and the Akademie der Bildenden Künste in Munich was discussed under Riemerschmid, but it would take until 1946 before the Kunstgewerbeschule was incorporated into the art academy. Cfr. A.K. Herber, *Frauen an deutschen Kunstakademien im 20. Jahrhundert: Ausbildungsmöglichkeiten für Künstlerinnen ab 1919 unter besonderer Berücksichtigung der süddeutschen Kunstakademien*, dissertation, Universität Heidelberg, Heidelberg, 2009. The Alte Nationalgalerie in Berlin recently devoted their exhibition *Kampf um Sichtbarkeit* to woman artists from before 1919. For the catalogue, see Y. Deseyve and R. Gleis (eds.), *Kampf um Sichtbarkeit: Künstlerinnen der Nationalgalerie vor 1919*, exh. cat., Reimer Verlag, Berlin, 2019.

³⁴ “Er fühlt deutlich die große unüberbrückbare Kluft zwischen Kunst und Leben, daß der Künstler nicht mitten im Leben stehen kann, sonst müßte er Kinder schaffen nicht Bilder. (...) Ich denke anders, denn ich bin nicht so Künstler, ich will schon leben und gebären, ich bin vom andern Geschlecht und wünsche es voll und ganz zu sein – so Gott will. – Die Kunst füllt mich jetzt aus, aber ich weiß, daß mich die Mutter noch viel mehr ausfüllen wird – so daß nichts mehr außer ihr da ist.” Notebook no. 8 (October 1915-June 1916) in the Gunta Stölzl Archive, pp. 76-77.

³⁵ For example, in the letter from 1915 to her friend Ingeborg quoted earlier she describes the perfect holiday as: “Skizzieren wandern rodeln raufen singen lesen einfach die ganze Herrlichkeit das geht mir

created outside an educational context, and mostly represent places and people that Stölzl encountered on her numerous travels in Bavaria and, during her work for the Red Cross, abroad. Rather than ‘finished’ works meant for selling or exhibiting, these are personal experiments, practices in representation, composition, use of color, different materials and techniques. They provide us with some vital information on Stölzl’s very early artistic development and interests. The following selection of these works represents some of the recurring themes in this part of Stölzl’s oeuvre.

One of the first themes that stands out in these works is Stölzl’s interest in working people, usually farmers that she encountered on the Bavarian countryside. The emphasis often lies on their act of collaboration, their working *together*, rather than on their individual characters, the human figures almost remaining anonymous. This is for example the case in *Threshing Women* (fig. 1), the date of which is estimated around 1915, and in *Peasant Family Cutting Wood* (fig. 2), made somewhere between 1914 and 1919. In both works, despite their difference in technique and materials, a large piece of equipment is centrally depicted, with figures grouped around it. In both works, the working people remain rather anonymous. In *Threshing Women* (fig. 1), the female figures appear exceptionally large, reminding us of the unusual figures of German Expressionism. The three women are all dressed in similar outfits and their faces are turned away from us. All the attention is directed towards the center of the composition, where the central action of threshing takes place. A predominantly primary color palette in this part of the painting contrasts with the secondary and tertiary colors in the architectural parts, where Stölzl used realistic hues of brown with black shadings. The different colors of a gouache paint mainly appear in planes, neatly put next to each other, recalling the technique of stained glass painting. During her studies at the Kunstgewerbeschule, Stölzl was skilled in this technique, but it was also present in the work of the Munich-based artists of der Blaue Reiter, who created reverse glass paintings (*‘Hinterglasmalerei’*) and also developed a style in their paintings that was evocative of this technique.³⁶ Similar to these paintings, Stölzl used black outlines that subdivide the scene into separate areas of vibrant colors, emulating the spatial compression of reverse glass painting (fig. 1). Indeed, her writings show that she was aware of contemporary artistic developments in Munich, and admired artists who participated in

nicht mehr aus dem Kopf.” Later she adds: “Ich skizziere jetzt viel im Freien zeichne viel aus der Erinnerung und hab’ halt immer eine gute Bildwirkung im Auge. Ich geh auch jetzt auf der Straße mit offenen Augen und schau mir die Menschen an, das ist furchtbar fein.”

³⁶ B. Herbert, *German Expressionism. Die Brücke and der Blaue Reiter*, Jupiter Books, London, 1983, p. 128; M. Moeller, *Der Blaue Reiter*, DuMont Buchverlag, Cologne, 1987, pp. 62-67.

Der Blaue Reiter, such as Franz Marc and Alfred Kubin. The famous almanac of Der Blaue Reiter, in which many works of its artists were reproduced, was published in 1913 through Piper in Munich. Although it is unknown when exactly she obtained it, Stölzl had this almanac on her bookshelves. Pointing towards one-to-one influences between her work and a particular artists in retrospect would be precarious, but it is certain that Stölzl was aware of what these artists in her hometown were doing.

In the drawing *Peasant Family Cutting Wood* (fig. 2), we find the same theme of a group of anonymized people occupied in a rural activity, centered around a large piece of equipment. Given the pile of tree trunks on the left, the figures are most likely occupied with woodworking; a traditional German craft. It is the action that is centralized, rather than the people performing it. The activity of working is further emphasized by the diagonal lines in the center of the drawing that make up the woodcutting tool. What is interesting here is that Stölzl depicts a collaboration of man and woman, both occupied with the same action. As in *Threshing Women* (fig. 1), the central activity is surrounded by architectural elements. Again, all the elements are only suggested by a few lines and strokes, while Stölzl experiments with different types of fillings. For example, the structure of the wall that makes up the house seems to be composed of nothing but a few smudges, and so are the strokes that suggest the leaves of the trees. Only half of the trunks on the pile on the left are filled in, in different manners, to suggest the texture of wood with only minimal means. The branches, the lantern and the windows are merely indicated by a few lines. Still, Stölzl manages to add contrast to the drawing, as a lighter gray alternates with darker patches of almost black. The result is a clever, minimal composition, that is nevertheless dynamic.

In Stölzl's writings we read that she greatly admired the attention that Van Gogh paid to the theme of the hard-working (wo)man, particularly the way in which he managed to capture "Arbeiter, Menschen unsrer Zeit".³⁷ In both German publications of Van Gogh's letters that were available at that time, black-and-white drawings are reprinted, which Van Gogh himself had included in some of his letters. These are sketches in a style that resembles Stölzl's drawings of everyday and almost anonymously working people. Given her oft-repeated enthusiasm regarding Van Gogh's letters, his oeuvre and his life, it is not unlikely that Stölzl was inspired to use a similar theme in a similar style. However, in both *Threshing Women* (fig. 1) and *Peasant Family* (fig. 2) Stölzl emphasizes the aspect of working *together*, and in *Peasant Family* specifically the collaboration of men and women.

³⁷ Notebook no. 8 (October 1915-June 1916) in the Gunta Stölzl Archive, p. 75.

One could argue that she applied her own personal touch to Van Gogh's idiom, by stressing this action of collaboration. Furthermore, although Stölzl explicitly expressed her admiration for Van Gogh, one should, again, remain careful in placing Stölzl back into an art historical context retrospectively, claiming a one-to-one influence of Van Gogh on her drawings. Stölzl's appreciation of the artist has to be situated within the context of the 'hype' in Germany: Van Gogh's remarkable reception as the father of modern art and as the artist as an emotionally disturbed, manically working, misunderstood genius, an image that his letters promoted and that Stölzl also voiced in her notebook. By this time, the 1910s in Germany, Van Gogh as the ideal artistic genius was firmly established in the artistic idiom of both art historians and visual artists. When discussing something as complex as 'influence' in this case, Stölzl's appreciation should at least be placed into this broader perspective, and the comparison made here is meant to illustrate some of her early sources of inspiration for her own work.

The horrors of the Great War

When discussing the start of the Bauhaus in Weimar, one cannot escape the enormous effect the First World War had had on the world, and on Germany in particular. It not only shaped the motivation and ideals of the school and its founders, but also the individual motives of its early students. The same can be said of Gunta Stölzl. In the spring of 1917, when many of the Munich-based avantgarde artists had been killed, such as August Macke, Franz Marc, and Albert Weisgerber, and while her only brother served at the front as a soldier, Stölzl decided to volunteer for the Red Cross, only returning to Munich after the war had ended.³⁸ Her diary from these months testifies to the horrors she witnessed, the suffering and death, the improvisation in makeshift field hospitals, the hopelessness, but also to the beauty of the different countries and landscapes, which she enjoyed immensely. Both sides are captured in her early sketches from this period. *Fontaine* (fig. 3), created, as the signature shows, in May 1918 in Fontaine-Notre-Dame, a French village close to Cambrai, evinces the horror of war. From Stölzl's diary, we learn that she arrived in the area in April 1918 and stayed there until her return home in September. The small village of Fontaine was the scene of horrible and intense fighting from November 1917 onwards during the Battle of Cambrai.³⁹ The church of Fontaine, the *Église de Saint-Martin*, was

³⁸ For more on the history of the German Red Cross, see S. Schomann, *Im Zeichen der Menschlichkeit. Geschichte und Gegenwart des Deutschen Roten Kreuzes*, Deutsche Verlagsanstalt, Munich, 2013. Stölzl's diary is quoted on pp. 166-167 and on p. 177.

³⁹ Cfr. B. Cooper, *The Ironclads of Cambrai*, Pen and Sword, Barnsley, 2010.

completely destroyed – as Stölzl has hauntingly illustrated here – and rebuilt in the 1920s, making the drawing an important artistic document of the First World War as well as a moving eyewitness account.

What stands out in this drawing, as in *Threshing Women* (fig. 1) and *Peasant Family* (fig. 2), is the different ways in which Stölzl suggests different textures with only minimal means, for example the expression of debris on the foreground, or the horizontal lines that constitute the remaining walls of the church on the far left versus the more densely colored parts of what once must have been the bell tower of the building to the right of it. In this drawing, Stölzl combines these textures with a dramatic contrast between white, gray and black parts. Whereas in the previous two works human beings were surrounded by architectural elements, here the architecture fills up a composition that is completely devoid of human presence. All these aspects together turn *Fontaine* (fig. 3) in a dramatically haunting yet silent testimony of the war that destroyed Europe. Her diary of the same date perfectly resonates with this drawing: “Alles was Menschenhände in langen Jahrzehnten geschaffen hatten, das lag mit grausam verstörtem Blick einsam da, ein Nichts mit toten, starren Augen.”⁴⁰

There are a dozen other drawings and watercolors from Stölzl’s hand that explicitly depict the horrors of the war, or that can be related directly to her diary from her months as a nurse for the Red Cross. Besides being of interest because of their artistic qualities, this group of unknown works on paper in particular could be regarded as interesting historical documents and might also be researched, published or exhibited as such – something that has not been done before. The same could be said of her diary, which is not only of a high literary quality, but also the historical account of an eyewitness. Both are largely unknown, but as a combined document, in which the writings and sketches accompany each other, Stölzl’s work from the war can illustrate the state of disillusion on the one hand, and the hope for a new, modern and constructive future on the other. The Bauhaus, established in the aftermath of the war, promised such a new future, and this may have been an important reason for Stölzl to leave Munich for Weimar. In this respect, I hope that opening up this specific part of Stölzl’s archive will not only help in shining a new light on her early artistic and literary talents and her interesting biography, but equally on the influence the Great War had on the early students of the Bauhaus.

⁴⁰ Gunta Stölzl in her diary, dated Cambrai, 11 May 1918.

Color experiments

Another important recurring aspect in Stölzl's early watercolors is her experimental use of colors. As with the similarities between Stölzl and Van Gogh, one should be careful in making one-to-one comparisons between Stölzl's work and artists whose work she looked at and appreciated: this would require expertized and more in-depth research. What I would like to do here, is to bring some of those color experiments out of the archives, to single out some of their intriguing aspects, and only suggest some possible sources of inspiration on the basis of Stölzl's writings quoted earlier. My main aim is to demonstrate that Stölzl was interested in developing her own modern color palette, an interest she would bring with her to the Bauhaus.

Stölzl's color experiments can often be found in her depictions of everyday architectural settings: views on villages, streets, and houses, mostly recognizable as Bavarian. Her painting *Giesing* (fig. 4), most likely created in 1915, contains one of the few buildings that can be identified, the Heilig-Kreuz-Kirche in the district of Giesing in Munich. The nineteenth-century church tower is painted in pink, purple, orange and yellow hues, rather than in its actual russet color. Also in the rest of the painting, Stölzl's palette is expressionist, consisting of complementary colors such as pink and orange versus blue in the block of houses depicted on the left, or purple and red versus green on the right side of the painting. This creates a warm and vivid atmosphere of the city on a sunny day. Many tones and hues are alternated and used close to each other in an almost analytical manner, an effect that is enhanced by the opaqueness of the paint (probably a gouache). This way of contrasting and experimenting with the effect colors could have on each other, rather than realistically using them, was already hinted at in *Threshing Women* (fig. 1) and is further expanded here. It was a central device in the work of many neo-impressionist painters as well as members of Der Blaue Reiter. As the forms that make up the picture are not particularly detailed – the shapes of the houses, for example, are reduced to a minimum – the detail and liveliness of this painting is the result of the contrasting color planes. Although the painting may appear somewhat rigid in terms of composition, it gives a good impression of Stölzl's very early color experiments.

A different palette is used in *View on a Courtyard* (fig. 5), in which Stölzl further explores the possibilities of colors and the medium. Compared to *Giesing* (fig. 4), the composition is freer, less rigid. The thick black outlines that often appear in her earlier watercolors, such as *Threshing Women* (fig. 1), have disappeared. Instead, Stölzl acts on the possibilities of her medium, as the colors naturally flow into each other. Again, shapes are largely reduced to a single and minimal color plane. Our attention is drawn to the parts depicted in the

primary colors of red, blue and yellow, which especially dominate the foreground, where a view on a courtyard is depicted. Here, especially visible on the left, where the painting is cut off by the side of a house, Stölzl experiments with the representation of natural light and shadows, much more than in *Giesing* (fig. 4) or *Treshing Women* (fig. 1) for example. The center of the composition is marked by a horizontal band of Prussian blue. It marks the transition from a palette consisting almost exclusively of primary colors on the foreground to a horizontal band of other color shades, such as purple, green and brown. From the empty space of the courtyard on the foreground, where part of the paper is left blank, Stölzl moves to packed rectangles in different colors, depicting a dense part of architecture, mainly consisting of roofs. This line of architecture is interrupted by the brown silhouette of a tree and by a thick, white horizontal shape, indicating fog, probably of a chimney or a factory. Here, Stölzl again makes use of the transparency that is characteristic of the watercolor paint used here, as one can still see the paint underneath it shine through. On the far background plane, something interesting happens. A yellow horizontal band indicates the horizon, representing stylized apartment buildings. On top of this band, Stölzl uses only a few lines in red to indicate architectural forms, merely suggesting them, a technique that does not recur in any of her earlier paintings. Compared to an earlier work such as *Giesing* (fig. 4), Stölzl here demonstrates that she not only starts to master the medium, but also further experiments with combining different non-realistic color palettes.

This mastering of her medium is even more visible in *Landscape at Sunset* (fig. 6), in which the many different colors of an impressive setting sun in the evening seem to tumble over each other. In the intense sky, the palette of contrasting colors appears again, but in a much more subtle and natural manner. In the lower part of the sky, a broad stroke of lemon yellow is set off by a cool blue, tending towards turquoise, while above it a darker blue appears, contrasting with a typically evening red and warm yellow. Skillfully subtle, red, yellow and blue again appear in other parts of the composition. Take for example the yellow house with its red roof on the left side of the painting with a blue shadow appearing next to it, or the blue shadows on the farm in the lower part. In a free and flowing composition, Stölzl uses numerous and whirling colors to bring us the experience of a summer sunset.

What is especially important in this demonstration of Stölzl's early color experiments is that she must have shown these or similar watercolors to Walter Gropius as part of her

portfolio in 1919, upon which she was admitted to the Bauhaus immediately.⁴¹ He also must have kept her on his radar, as he asked Stölzl in the spring of 1920 to partake in the foundation of the women's class. This could not have been on the basis of Stölzl's textile skills or knowledge of weaving, in which she had not received extensive training at the Kunstgewerbeschule. Color theory was one of the core elements of Bauhaus education, as taught by Johannes Itten, Josef Albers, Paul Klee, and Wassily Kandinsky, among others, in the preliminary course as well as outside of it.⁴² The influence of these teachers on Gunta Stölzl and the other weaving students at the Bauhaus has been discussed by others⁴³, but always in terms of a one-way relationship of a teacher teaching a student. What is overlooked is that Stölzl did not come to the Bauhaus a tabula rasa: she had clearly already been researching new experimental uses of colors, as her watercolors from the years 1914 to 1919 confirm, and as her early writings tentatively allude to, given the preference she showed there for certain artists. For Gropius, this was probably an important aspect that appealed to him in Stölzl's early work, and it may have contributed to him admitting her to the Bauhaus and to assigning her a leading position with responsibilities early on in Weimar.⁴⁴ The lesson that Stölzl's archives thus teach us, is that the Bauhaus was not merely shaped top-down, by its leaders, teachers, or constitutions, but also bottom-up, by its students and the artistic baggage each one of them brought with them to the school.⁴⁵ Whereas the pre-Bauhaus history of the early masters has received attention, this is not the

⁴¹ I. Radewaldt, *Gunta Stölzl*, p. 23. Unfortunately, Radewaldt does not discuss these works and their artistic qualities in great depth.

⁴² Cfr. H. Düchting, *Farbe am Bauhaus: Synthese und Synästhesie*, Gebr. Mann, Berlin, 1996.

⁴³ Cfr. I. Radewaldt, *Gunta Stölzl*, pp. 39-45 on Johannes Itten, pp. 52-57 on Paul Klee, and pp. 58-61 on Wassily Kandinsky; Radewaldt, 'Unterricht am Bauhaus', exh. cat. *Gunta Stölzl. Meisterin am Bauhaus Dessau*, Verlag Gerd Hatje, Ostfildern, 1997, pp. 104-111, where Itten, Klee, and Kandinsky are discussed in relation to Stölzl. For a more general discussion of Klee's influence on the weaving workshop, see J. Anger, 'Klees Unterricht in der Webereiwerkstatt des Bauhauses', exh. cat. *Das Bauhaus webt. Die Textilwerkstatt am Bauhaus*, G+H Verlag, Berlin, 1998, pp. 33-41.

⁴⁴ Cfr. I. Radewaldt, *Gunta Stölzl*, pp. 49-50.

⁴⁵ Stölzl was certainly not the only one who had already followed some artistic education before going to the Bauhaus. In Germany, there were more students whose studies had been disrupted by the war, and who switched to something else, and especially something completely new, after the war had ended. Stölzl herself refers to this in her article on the development of the Bauhaus weaving workshop, see G. Stölzl, 'die entwicklung der bauhausweberei', *bauhaus zeitschrift für gestaltung* no. 2, July 1931, p. 2.

case for the early students in Weimar, who must have contributed in no small manner to shaping the school.⁴⁶

The power of the archive

Stölzl's early work and writings discussed here form only the top of the iceberg of an oeuvre that spans a large part of the twentieth century. Although far from complete, my findings mark the start of uncovering the full image of Gunta Stölzl's artistic trajectory, by exploring both writings and works on paper from a new time frame (1914-1919). Her archives, which are extensive and well-preserved, prove a fruitful ground for reaping this more complete picture of Stölzl's career, but there is still much work to be done. 2019 was the year in which female *Bauhäusler* were finally given their place into the historiography of the school. Now, two years later, I propose to take this further: it is time to expand the research output on female *Bauhäusler* beyond the walls of the school. As a side effect, by looking at the work Bauhaus students, and especially female students, created before entering the school, that is, unpacking their artistic luggage, an even more complete historiography of the school and its student body may unfold as well. Archival research can make vital contributions to this process of uncovering. Now that the dust of the 100th anniversary of the Bauhaus has settled down, we may start bringing up wonderful findings testifying to these women's individual careers.

⁴⁶ P. Rössler and A. Blümm, 'Soft Skills and Hard Facts: A Systematic Assessment of the Inclusion of Women at the Bauhaus', *Bauhaus Bodies*, edited by E. Otto and P. Rössler, Bloomsbury Visual Arts, New York, 2019, p. 5.

APPENDIX

Credits: Gunta Stölzl, © VG Bild-Kunst, Bonn

Photo credits: Estate Gunta Stölzl, 2021

These and other works by Gunta Stölzl can be found in her work catalogue, please visit <https://www.guntastolzl.org/About/Catalogue/>

FIG. 1, Gunta Stölzl, Threshing Women, ca. 1915, watercolor

FIG. 2, Gunta Stözl, Peasant Family Cutting Wood, 1914-1919, pencil sketch

FIG. 3, Gunta Stözl, *Fontaine*, 1918, pencil sketch

FIG. 4, Gunta Stözl, Giesing, ca. 1915, watercolor

FIG. 5, Gunta Stölzl, View on a Courtyard, 1917-1919, watercolor

FIG. 6, Gunta Stölzl, *Landscape at Sunset*, 1917-1919,

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